

TECHNOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF OBTAINING ALMMC – THE MODIFICATION OF ALSI MATRIX ALLOY

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ABSTRACT

In the liquid phase process of obtaining the composites important phenomena are associated with wettability of reinforcing phase with the melt. Proper preparation of both, the matrix alloy and ceramic reinforcement phase are important. In the technological process based on the stir-casting (suspension method) appropriate preparation of matrix alloy is decisive importance for the permanent connection between the ceramic particles and the liquid matrix. The procedure developed by the authors (pat. no. P.391006)) includes a step of removing the solid inclusions and hydrogen refining alloy base by purging Ar and modify the chemical composition of the base AlSi7Mg alloy. 30 minutes Ar refining takes place by barbotage with a stirrer, which through the gas flows in an amount of 1 dm³/h. Then, after removal from the molten metal a slag layer, chemical composition of the alloy is modified by the addition of Mg and Sr. To increase the volume of Mg to 2% wt. by AlMg25 masteralloy is used, while AlSr10 masteralloy is used for the enrichment of the composition to Sr 0.03% wt. In order to homogenize the chemical composition of the alloy is mixed under reduced pressure (500 hPa) for another 30 min. These treatments modify the surface tension at the liquid metal in the system by improving wetting of the ceramic. Thus prepared, the matrix alloy allows the preparation of hybrid composites reinforced with a mixture of SiC particles or SiC + Cp + GR. After 2 hours of homogenization under reduced pressure (500 hPa) it is possible to cast composite suspension.

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